

ANALYSIS OF PERFORMANCE INDICATORS OF FIXED ASSETS (IN THE CASE OF BUDGET ENTERPRISES)

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Abstract

In this article, on the example of budget enterprises, fixed assets, their composition, efficiency of fixed assets, their indicators, analysis of the composition of fixed assets (type), renewal and withdrawal coefficients, technical condition and movement indicators of fixed assets are presented, the data were researched using exact values.

Key words

financial opportunities, fixed assets, capital investments, enterprise balance sheet, financial economy, renewal coefficient, exit coefficient, wear coefficient, serviceability coefficient.

In the modern economic conditions, regardless of the type of activity, the effective operation of the enterprise of any organizational and legal form is a necessary condition for its existence. The composition, activity of any basic funds (type) should be useful, and the purpose of any production is profit. Achieving this goal depends on a large number of factors and is related to the general organization of production, the use of high technologies, financial capabilities, as well as the technical equipment of the enterprise.¹²¹

The successful operation of the enterprise is related to the effective use of all property and, first of all, fixed assets and working capital.

Fixed assets are material values used as labor tools that work for a long time in an unchanging natural form and transfer their value to the cost of products, work, and services in parts.

In the practice of accounting and statistics, fixed assets include labor tools with a service life of at least one year and a value not less than the specified norm. According to the nature of participation of basic funds in the process of extended reproduction, they are divided into productive and non-productive basic funds.

Production fixed assets perform a function in the field of material production, repeatedly participate in the production process, gradually wear out, and their value is divided into parts depending on the use of the manufactured product. They are replenished at the expense of capital investments.

Non-producing capital funds are residential buildings, children's and sports facilities, other cultural and household objects on the balance sheet of the enterprise. The role of fixed assets in the labor process is that they form the production-technical base and determine the production capacity of the enterprise and the level of technical equipment of labor. The accumulation of basic funds and the increase in the technical equipment of labor enriches the labor process, gives labor a creative character, and increases the cultural and technical level of society.

A large and most important part of the society's material resources is embodied in the main funds. They constitute the main part of the country's national wealth.

Basic production funds should be systematically updated. Increasing the basic funds, especially labor tools, improving their quality based on the latest technical and scientific achievements, increasing the technical equipment of labor, and producing quality products with less labor are considered to be the most important conditions.

Production (type) composition of basic funds is a share.

The most important factors affecting the specific structure of fixed assets are:

The analysis and evaluation of the financial and economic activity of the budget enterprise is based on the information supply system. It provides a targeted process of selecting information indicators in the study of the management of the budget enterprise and comprehensive review of its positions using various methods, models, financial instruments.

In the analysis and control of the financial and economic activity of the enterprise, first of all, external environmental factors and key production indicators are taken into account. It includes the composition of the property and the sources of its formation, assessment of fixed assets. It is also necessary to determine the efficiency of the use of the active part of assets (the fixed assets in use are taken into account) and analyze the composition of groups of fixed assets.

Table 1

Analysis of the composition of fixed assets on the example of a budget enterprise (Bukhara Technical College of Architecture and Construction).¹²²

Indicators.	2021 y, %	2022 y, %	Rate of change of indicators, in %, %
1. Buildings and structures	44,43	39,96	-4,47
2. Land plots	17,67	15,89	-1,78
3. Machinery and equipment	30,94	37,75	6,81
4. Vehicles	1,14	1,03	-0,11
5. Production and household inventory	5,77	5,35	-0,42
Total	100	100	0

As can be seen from the table, in the example of the budget organization, buildings and structures had the largest share in fixed assets at the end of 2022, making up 39,96%. The share of machines and equipment was 37,75%, land plots – 15,89%, production and household appliances – 5,35%, vehicles – 1,03%. Compared to 2021, the share of buildings in the main funds decreased by 4,47%, land plots by 1,78%, vehicles by 0,11%, production and household appliances by 0,42%, but the share of machinery and equipment increased by 6,81% can reach.

Table 2

Analysis of the movement and technical condition of the main funds on the example of budget enterprises.

Indicators.	Update coefficient.		Rate of change of indicators, in %, %
	2021 y, %	2022 y, %	

¹²² <https://buxarxtex.uz>

1. Buildings and structures	7.65	6.87	-1.67
2. Land plots	0	0	0
3. Machinery and equipment	36.54	36.86	0.52
4. Vehicles	0	0	0
5. Production and household inventory	2.53	2.16	-0.37

According to the data in the table, in 2022, the coefficient of renewal of buildings and structures from all the main funds of budget enterprises decreased by 1,67%, but the coefficient of renewal of the active part of the main enterprises (machines and equipment) increased by 0,52% can reach.

Table 3

Analysis of the change in the coefficient of departure of fixed assets from 2021 to 2022 on the example of budget enterprises.

Indicators.	2021 y, %	2022 y, %	Rate of change of indicators, in %, %
1. Buildings and structures	7,64	8.03	0,39
2. Land plots	0	0	0
3. Machinery and equipment	39.02	39,45	0,43
4. Vehicles	0	2.26	-2.26
5. Production and household inventory	2,52	2,38	-0.14

From the data in the table, it can be seen that in the case of budget enterprises, the coefficients of fixed assets have changed as follows. The output coefficient of buildings and structures increased by 0,39%, and the output coefficient of machines and equipment increased by 0,43%. However, the output coefficient of vehicles decreased by 2,26%, and the output coefficient of production and household inventories decreased by 0,14%.

Table 4

Analysis of the technical condition of the main funds. (in the case of budget enterprises).

Indicators.	2021 y, %		2022 y, %		Rate of change of indicators, in %, %	
	Validity coefficient	Validity coefficient				
	.	.	.	.	.	.

1. Buildings and structures	11,54	88,46	12,99	87,01	1,45	-1,45
2. Land plots	0	0	0	0	0	0
3. Machinery and equipment	47,27	55,35	52,73	44,65	10,7	-10,7
4. Vehicles	100	100	0	0	0	0
5. Production and household inventory	72,16	27,84	84,46	15,54	12,3	-12,3
Total	57,74	42,25	63,2	36,8	5,46	-5,45

From the data of the table, it can be seen that the analysis of the indicators of the technical condition of the main means of the organization has changed as follows. In the process of reductions in the field of education, negative changes were observed in the state of the main means of the organization. In all fixed assets, an increase in the coefficient of wear was observed, and a decrease in the level of serviceability occurred. In the composition of the main funds, the efficiency coefficient of production and economic inventories was equal to 12.3% in the highest percentage. The lowest percentage coefficient of suitability was observed in buildings and structures and was equal to 1.45%.

It can be seen from the above analysis that we would like to make the following suggestions and recommendations in order to increase the efficiency of the use of fixed assets and further improve accounting in the case of budget enterprises:

- 1) release the organization from excess equipment, machines and other fixed assets or rent them;
- 2) timely and high-quality implementation of planned preventive and capital repair works;
- 3) purchase of high-quality fixed assets;
- 4) increase the level of qualification of service personnel;
- 5) timely renewal of the main means, especially the active part, in order to prevent excessive spiritual and physical wear and tear;
- 6) introduction of new equipment and progressive technology - low waste, no waste and fuel economy;
- 7) improvement of production and labor organization in order to reduce the loss of working time and downtime in the operation of machines and equipment. One of the main conditions for increasing the efficiency of the processes of

reproduction of fixed assets is the optimal service life of fixed assets, first of all, their active part, in accordance with the initial technological purpose. At the same time, both the reduction and increase of the service life affect the reproduction of tools and the efficiency of their use in different ways.

Any enterprise, regardless of the form of education and type of activity, must constantly take into account the movement of its main funds, their composition and condition, efficiency of use. This information allows the enterprise to determine ways and reserves to increase the efficiency of the use of fixed assets, in addition, to timely identify and correct negative changes that will have serious consequences for the successful operation of the enterprise in the future.

Among the directions for increasing the efficiency of the use of the main production funds, the main ones related to innovation, technical re-equipment and investment policy can be distinguished. The main methods of increasing the efficiency of the use of the main production funds are as follows:

- accelerating the replacement of outdated, inefficient equipment with progressive, more efficient, economical equipment;
- construction of new facilities with full use of the capacity and labor resources of existing enterprises;
- reduction of net capital investments;
- to improve the quality of raw materials, to ensure environmental cleanliness of the main production funds and materials;
- priority of capital investments in small-scale and waste-free production, energy and fuel-saving technologies;
- increase the level of transformation and digitization of production.

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